

PD ON AN IOT-CLASS PROCESSOR

Miller Puckette
UCSD
msp@ucsd.edu

Kerry L. Hagan
UNiversity of Limerick
Kerry.Hagan@ul.ie

ABSTRACT

Audio installations and other sound art projects sometimes call for large numbers of inexpensive digital audio systems. We have adapted the Pure Data environment to an embedded system using the Espressif ESP32 processor. We find that it is possible to run Pd on an ESP32-based audio development board costing about 20 USD. We were able to build a complete system for a particular art project that can respond to wireless commands and synthesize a continuous stream of sound, while only dissipating about 925 milliwatts. This approach should be adaptable to a range of other possible sound art projects.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper is intended as an update to a long-running story, in which digital audio signal processing becomes perpetually less expensive and more physically portable. In the last decade or so, things have progressed to the point that the most difficult aspect of audio processing is sometimes bringing electric power and communications to the physical location where audio is to be recorded, processed, or played. For example, in a recently built portable multi-channel listening space [1], dozens of standalone receivers were placed at regularly spaced points in the inside of a dome. Rather than run power and signal cables to all the points, the more practical option was to use solar-charged batteries and WIFI connections using Audio Over Osc (AOO [2]).

In such situations each node must be equipped with an inexpensive processor, powerful enough to do whatever processing is needed onsite, able to support audio I/O, and dissipating as little power as possible. One also has to either choose or write a framework for interactive control of the device over a wireless connection such as WIFI or Bluetooth.

The artist must then decide to either use an existing real-time program to provide the desired DSP and control capabilities, or else to develop a program from scratch. Here there is a trade-off between memory efficiency and design convenience. At one extreme, writing your own program from scratch is likely to be time-consuming (particularly since the debugging tools available might not be as well oiled as on a workstation)—but at the same time

you get very tight control of CPU and memory usage. As we move along the spectrum of computer music environments, we encounter first csound, which is certainly the most compact and memory-efficient one in wide use today, through RTCMIX and Pure Data, then onto higher-level, more highly automated systems such as supercollider.

The impetus for the work described here was a recent sound installation project that required outputting audio from about 20 ugly throw pillows. To achieve spatial effects such as panning between pillows, their audio outputs must all be synchronized to within a millisecond or so but need not be synchronized at the sample level. Some mode of intercommunication is needed to coordinate them. Although we have not placed sensors inside the pillows, this remains an open possibility for future versions of the piece.

We chose to use Pure Data, as probably the highest-level tool that would fit into 1/2 megabyte of data memory. It has proved to be a tight but manageable fit.

Pure Data, being open-source, has been adapted to a variety of situations, some of which are ultra-portable implementations that take advantage of its reasonably small memory footprint [3]. An early example was Pure Data Anywhere (“PDA”) [4], in which a version of Pd ran on portable electronic devices that typically had 8 or 16 MB of memory to share between code, data memory, and a filesystem. Here the main limitation was not memory size but floating-point speed; since the personal devices of that era did not normally contain floating-point units, the signal processing code in Pd was adapted to run on fixed-point audio samples. Such an approach would be of interest even today if one wanted to run Pd directly inside an earbud whose processors also normally offer only fixed-point computation. (These devices can run on a fraction of the power that we will be using in the work described here.) At least one fully realized project used PDA running on a Gumstick computer [5].

At about the same time a quite different project, also based on Pd, was installed in the New York Times lobby [6]. Here the 560 processors are wired (so no batteries nor wireless networking needed) but on the other hand, the installation, part of a building lobby, was designed to run for at least 50 years. There is visual as well as audible output. The cost of the project was much less constrained, but the maintainability requirement drove many design choices. Again, a fixed-point version of Pd was used and the audio processing was kept simple to run on the available CPU.

Over the ensuing years Pd has often been used on cell-phones and tablet computers, for example using MobMuPlat [7]. Here the affordance is not so much the cheapness and portability of the system (typically in the

Copyright: © 2022 Miller Puckette et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

hundreds of US dollars), but the fact that many or most people using this platform will run it on their own tablet or cellphone. The artist thereby cedes a great deal of control over the listening environment and other aspects of the work, but the incremental cost and effort required to install such a system can be kept quite small.

A new option, the one we will study here, is to run Pd on a recently announced processor family, the Espressif ESP32. This comes in uniprocessor and two-processor models running between 160 and 240 MHz, with excellent floating-point performance. It is explicitly designed with embedded systems in mind, and so has memory-mapped flash memory (typically 2 or 4 megabytes), from which it runs instructions directly. Although it has only up to 520 kilobytes of RAM, this is only used as data memory and so the overall memory size might be considered as comparable to the original prototype ISPW. At first glance, then, running Pd on an ESP32-based embedded system would seem a viable option.

2. THE HARDWARE

The Espressif ESP32 system was first announced in 2016 and is now available in a wide variety of packages. Some of these packages incorporate the ESP32-VROOM module that combines the ESP32 processor with a radio subsystem that supports WIFI and/or Bluetooth. The ESP32-VROOM module is clocked at 160 MHz, has two processors with floating-point units, and can run an operating system, FreeRTOS.

On top of FreeRTOS, Espressif supplies a development environment and additional libraries that implement WIFI and Bluetooth, drivers for I2S, I2C, and UARTS, and the FAT filesystem that can be mounted from an SD card. (There are other goodies as well but these are all that will concern us here).

An artist wishing to incorporate the ESP32-VROOM might wish to start with a development board with integrated audio, microSD reader, and battery management. These are available from Espressif under the names LyraT and LyraT Mini, and offer up to 2 channels of audio input and output for about 20 USD.

Alternatively, or perhaps in a later, more ambitious project, an artist can add one or more of their own audio I/O devices to a stripped-down development board such as the ESP32-VROOM-E32, which adds little more than a USB programming port and a large number of breakout pins.

3. EXAMPLE USING THE LYRAT BOARD

The particular project that led us to port Pd to the ESP32 required assembling dozens of copies of a physically portable system having wireless communication with a nearby computer, a local filesystem, one channel of audio output, and the ability to run for 8 hours at a time on a single battery charge. Our hardware consists of a 3.7 volt, 2000 mAH rechargeable battery, a LyraT Mini board (a one-channel, reduced-footprint version of the LyraT), and a tiny loudspeaker. To conserve power we used Bluetooth instead of

WIFI and wrote a small routine to send and receive Pd messages in ASCII. With Bluetooth, the microSD card, and the audio output all in use, the system dissipates about 250 milliamps of power (so about 925 milliwatts). Depending on how the battery and speaker are sourced, each system costs about 30 to 40 USD to build.

The systems are easily concealed inside our ugly throw pillows. We use a single Raspberry Pi computer to coordinate the ensemble. This central CPU is hidden within Bluetooth range of the pillows but need not operate on battery power (and so the 5 to 10 watts typically dissipated by Pis is not problematic). The Pis send control messages to each pillow over a Bluetooth virtual serial line. Among other things, messages to the pillows can contain the patch they will run, so that the patch itself can be edited and modified offline and updated on the Pis as needed. Sending the patch over Bluetooth as a sequence of ordinary Pd messages saves us having to upload it onto the many individual microSD cards and allows for easy on-site customization during the installation process.

4. CONCLUSION

It is feasible to run Pure Data on inexpensive, portable, low-power hardware systems. The user develops a Pd Patch on a general-purpose computer and subsequently runs it on the embedded system without the use of a graphical user interface. The techniques described here can feasibly be used in a wide variety of artistic applications.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] W. Ritsch, "Der dom als virtuelle klangwelt," 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://algo.mur.at/projects/klangdom/shor.pdf/@@download/file/shortdesc.pdf>
- [2] —, "Towards a message based audio system," 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://lac.linuxaudio.org/2014/papers/36.pdf>
- [3] H.-C. Steiner, "Building your own instrument with pd," in *Proceedings of the 1st International Pd Convention, Graz, Austria. Citeseer*, 2005.
- [4] G. Geiger, "The search for usability and flexibility in computer music systems," in *Bang: Pure Data*. Hofheim am Taunus: Wolke Verlag, 2004, pp. 121–134.
- [5] J. Stevens, M. Flynn, T. Humphrey *et al.*, "Distributed wireless duplex audio networks in a travelling art work: the megaphone project," 2007.
- [6] M. Hansen, B. Rubin, E. Studio, H.-C. Steiner, T. Walker, and P. Electricicks, "Words to look at, words to listen to: Designing a "proliphonic" display for the lobby of the new york times building," in *2008 Linux Audio Conference*. Citeseer, 2008.
- [7] D. Iglesia and I. Intermedia, "The mobility is the message: The development and uses of mobmuplat," in *Pure Data Conference (PdCon16)*. New York, 2016.